
RISK MANAGEMENT THROUGH CONTRACTUAL RISK MITIGATION CLAUSES: A REVIEW OF THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK AND BEST PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

There are many purposes that a well-drafted contract serves, but the main aim behind drafting a contract is to safeguard ourselves from all the legal problems that may arise in future on account of poor penmanship or confusion between parties. Modern multinational companies and governments are smart enough to hire diligent legal professionals, who are getting paid to review and write such contracts that may help their client to be in a dominant position. In such a scenario it gets really important for a layman or even a nascent legal professional to learn how to obviate such liabilities that may arise for them or their client. This paper talks about “Various clauses that can be used for Risk mitigation in a contract” and talks about the roots of such clauses in the Indian Contract Act, of 1872. Also, it delves into various case laws pertaining to the given sections as well as how these case laws have developed the ambit of the usage of these provisions. It will be correct to say at this stage that as a rule as long as a clause is conspicuously or explicitly not written in a contract, during execution also, it cannot be valid to imply such a clause in the contract, without the presence of any such action on part of any party. This paper, keeping the above-said rule in mind talks about clauses that will be surely beneficial for the party/parties who will enact such clauses in their contract.

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I. WHAT IS RISK MITIGATION IN A CONTRACT?

Risk mitigation clauses are neither classified nor defined under the Indian Contract Act, of 1872. Yet, there are specific provisions in the act which are the basis of such clauses. A risk mitigation clause in a contract is a contractual provision designed to reduce or minimize the likelihood of potential risks and create mechanisms to address them. These clauses are tailored to the parties' particular needs and aim to minimize potential risks that may arise during the agreement.³ Various types of risks can be countered by such clauses. They might include financial risks, legal risks as well as operational and reputational risks. Some standard risk mitigation clauses in a contract like force majeure, liability clause and inter alia others will be discussed in great length. Also, one point that needs to be understood is that not only the standard clauses but also a customized clause in a contract shall be construed as a risk mitigation clause only. For example, if a company hires only those contractors who have certain safety standards and have their worker's insurance done, then this pre-condition can also be comprehended as a mitigation clause. Let us now understand the various types of Risk Mitigation clauses:

II. LIABILITY CLAUSE IN A CONTRACT

Why are people emphasizing more towards incorporating LLPs (Limited Liability Partnerships) & companies? The primary reason is because of the limited liability that the members have in such entities, i.e. the personal assets of the members cannot be used to reimburse the loans and liabilities of the company. As of January 2023, out of 1.51 million companies incorporated in India, only 296 were having unlimited liability.⁴ In a similar fashion to mitigate liability, contracting parties can also invoke a liability clause in their Contract, so that they can be held liable only for a certain amount. Liability clauses find their roots in **section 74** of the Indian Contract Act, of 1872.⁵

For ease of reference, the section has been reproduced.

[When a contract has been broken, if a sum is named in the contract as the amount to be paid in case of such breach, or if the contract contains any other stipulation by way of penalty, the

³ Ken Button, Contract Risk Management: 10 Best Practices To Keep Your Business Safe, Contract Safe, <https://www.contractsafe.com/blog/contract-risk-management> (last visited June 11, 2024).

⁴ India: number of active registered companies by type 2024 , <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1008330/india-number-of-registered-active-companies-by-type/> (last visited June 11, 2024).

⁵ Indian Contract Act, section 74, 1872 (India).

party complaining of the breach is entitled, whether or not actual damage or loss is proved to have been caused thereby, to receive from the party who has broken the contract reasonable compensation not exceeding the amount so named or, as the case may be, the penalty stipulated for.]

This section is eloquent enough to walk us through the liability clause. It expressly mentions the fact that an amount not more than what has been written shall be given by the party who has breached a contract. So, even if a breach has happened, still a liability clause will be a safeguard and the party will not accrue a penny more than the amount that has been mentioned in the contract.⁶ Henceforth saving the party from unlimited liability on their part.

The only thing that needs to be looked upon is that any limiting liability clause should not violate any law or go against the statutory provisions. **Section 23** of the act expressly bars such contracts which are against public policy or are immoral in nature. In the case of **Central Inland Water Transport Corporation. Vs. Brojo Nath Ganguly**⁷ it is stated by the Supreme Court that an unequal bargaining power in a contract shall make the contract void. Many times, what the court has seen is that the great economic differences between the parties can sometimes lead to one party getting the upper hand on the clauses of the contract.⁸ So even if there is a liability clause in a contract if one party may prove that the other party has not given their free will towards the same clause or due to one party holding an upper hand either in monetary ways or other ways has compelled the aggrieved party to enter in a contract then the contract may be rendered void. Also, in the case of **Simplex Concrete Piles (India) Limited v. Union of India**⁹ the Delhi High Court gave clarity on the situations when the clauses of the contracts need to be neglected as they are against public policy. In the same case, the government entered into a contract with a contractor stating clauses detrimental to the contractor. One of such clauses was that if the contractor is unable to complete the contract within the stipulated time for reasons on which he has no control and even if an extension has been granted for such delays then also, he will not be entitled to any compensation. The Court abandoning such a clause emphasized that such clauses are not equitable in law and obliterates

⁶ Akash Saha, Limitation Of Liability- A Safety Net For The Contracting Party, ManuPatra (last visited June 11, 2024).

⁷ Central Inland Water Transport Corporation. V. Brojo Nath Ganguly, (1986) 3 SCC 15.

⁸ Raunak Dhillon & Ananya Choudhary, [Does Non-Stamping of a Contract Render an Arbitration Clause Contained in it Unenforceable? The Supreme Court Says Yes](#), Cyril Amarchand Mangaldas| India corporate Law, (last visited June 11, 2024). [Does Non-Stamping of a Contract Render an Arbitration Clause Contained in it Unenforceable? The Supreme Court Says Yes | India Corporate Law \(cyrilamarchandblogs.com\)](#)

⁹ Simplex Concrete Piles (India) Limited v. Union of India, ILR (2010) II Delhi 699.

the entire essence of the contract. Such clauses which have given no remedy to an aggrieved party without any of its fault are against public policy and shall be construed as void by virtue of section 23 of the Indian Contract Act, 1872.

III. FORCE MAJEURE CLAUSE

Force majeure is a French term that in the Literal sense means “greater force”. These are unforeseeable circumstances that prevent someone from fulfilling a contract. Section 32 of the Indian Contract Act discusses contingent contracts. These contracts are dependent upon the happening or non-happening of another contract. Similarly, section 56 of the contract act talks about agreements to do impossible events. A basic proposition that can be drawn is that whenever an express or implied clause has been given in a contract regarding the happening/non-happening of an event and then due to some unforeseeable reasons the contractual obligation doesn't take place then, it will come under section 32 of the act, whereas if there is something that has happened outside the purview of the contemplation of the parties or “dehors” then that shall be construed under the realms of section 56 of the Indian Contract act.¹⁰ This bifurcation has been created by the case of **Satyabrata Ghose vs Mugneeram Bangur**¹¹. Putting a force majeure clause can save a party from unwanted liabilities that may accrue if a party is unable to pass the strict tests under section 56 of the act. What this means is that for a contract to be frustrated under section 56 of the act it has to be proved that the impediment to a duty to perform the contract is so fundamental in nature that in any case whatsoever happens, the contract can now not be done with.

In the English case of **Tsakiroglou & Co Ltd v Noblee Thorl GmbH**¹² it has been stated that a mere possibility of some inconvenience to complete an act in the contract cannot frustrate the contract. In this case, due to the fact that the Suez Canal was inoperable, the defendant denied the contract on the grounds of frustration. It was held that an inability to go through Suez Canal doesn't mean that the contract cannot be completed by going through “The Cape of Good Hopes”. Now, let us relate this case to the pandemic times when the Government of India, through its memo no. F. 18/4/2020 PPD (Issued by the Ministry of Finance) declared that the

¹⁰ Saikrishna & Associates, May the Force (Majeure) Be with You, Mondaq, (last visited June 11, 2024). <https://www.mondaq.com/india/operational-impacts-and-strategy/1369284/may-the-force-majeure-be-with-you>

¹¹ Satyabrata Ghose V. Mugneeram Bangur & Co, AIR 1954 SC 44.

¹² Tsakiroglou & Co Ltd v Noblee Thorl GmbH, 1962] AC 93 [1961] 2 All ER 179.

disruption of supply chains caused by the Covid-19 outbreak should be considered as a natural disaster and be covered under the force majeure Clause, and parties should invoke it wherever necessary. This notification was limited only to the supply chain and adhering to the principle stated in the abovementioned case it should be clear that the pandemic cannot be used as a shield to complete the obligations that have been stated in the contract. The Bombay High Court in the case of **Standard Retail Pvt. Ltd vs. M/s. G.S. Global Corp and Ors**¹³ Clearly stated that even with a “FORCE MAJEURE” clause in a contract, a party during COVID-19 cannot be relieved of its burden of paying the other party and only those acts which overtly disallow a party to complete their contractual obligation may be considered.¹⁴ It can be said that commercial hardship shall not be a reasonable ground to support the frustration of the contract and should not act as an excuse for performance. The Courts have no general inclination to pardon a party from the performance of its part of the contract merely because its performance has become onerous on account of an unforeseen turn of events. Parties are under an obligation to complete their part of the contract against all mishappenings, within a foreseeable limit. It is only in situations where the situation is so erroneous that even through all the options available, the parties will not be able to complete the contract.

IV. WAIVER CLAUSES IN A CONTRACT

Waiver is a term used to define the forbearance of right; where one party voluntarily agrees to grant a concession to the other contracting party with regards to the performance of a contract it can be said that a waiver has happened by one party. There are three ways present in the section 63 of the Indian Contract Act by which a promisee may renounce or waive off his right. The section provides three conditions.

The first being, when “dispense with or remit, wholly or in part, the performance made to him”. This means that a promisee has given the promisor an option to either pay a smaller amount for his full claim or the promisee may forego the entire amount that he is entitled to take. In the second aspect under the same section the promisee is allowed to extend the time for his claim. That being said, the promisor now has some more time pay the same amount. In

¹³Standard Retail Pvt. Ltd vs. M/s. G.S. Global Corp and Ors, Order dated April 8, 2020, passed by the Bombay High Court in Commercial Arbitration Petition (Lodging) No. 404 of 2020.

¹⁴ Adarsh Saxena, FORCE MAJEURE IN THE TIMES OF COVID -19, Cyril Amarchand Mangaldas| India corporate Law, (last visited June 11,2024).
<https://corporate.cyrilamarchandblogs.com/2020/05/supremecourt-domestic-award-set-aside-as-being-pervese/>

the third and the last instance, the promisee can accept any amount that he wishes to, in his satisfaction.

The Supreme Court through various judgements, with time has developed jurisprudence about what amounts to waiver and what are the essentials to constitute “waiver of rights”. The Supreme Court in the judgment of **M/S Motilal Padampat Sugar Mills vs State Of Uttar Pradesh And Ors**,¹⁵ has stated that albeit there is no difference between implied or expressed waiver, what will be integral is the presence of the intention with an express knowledge.¹⁶ Also, in the case of **P. Dasa Muni Reddy vs P. Appa Rao**¹⁷ the court reiterating the above principle, also added that the act must be voluntary in nature. Also, the three essentials i.e intention, knowledge and voluntary act were developed in this judgment. Moreover silence can never amount to a waiver of a right. The kerala high court in **Rev. Msgr. Philip Njaralakkatt v. State of Kerala**¹⁸ held that a mere fact that a person has done something in the past, which he was exempted from doing, cannot be deciphered as a waiver of his/her right.

V. NOTICE AND COMMUNICATION CLAUSES

It is always better to have a notice clause in a contract. A very simple example of how a notice clause works is that when one party has drafted a notice clause, which says that “for a mere default in payment, no party can sue the other without giving a reasonable notice”. Such notices give ample time to the parties to either reconcile or the party that has done the Breach can anticipate a law suit and avail required legal remedy for the same. Simultaneously, they may also agree to Alternate Dispute mechanisms like Arbitration. There could be notices for termination of contract, for renewal of contract, or in a lessor-lessee agreement, the lessor might need to give notice to the lessee before entering the premises. These are some of the examples of how a notice clause is put into effect in a contract.

The problem arises when a notice is sent but not served. Let us understand by what the difference is, let us consider the Civil Procedure Code, Order 5 Rule 17 and Order 5 rule 20 talks about a notice being served. Though the reference under the civil procedure code is related to summons, the principle present is of great importance for our topic. If, only sending was a compliance, then rule 17 and rule 20 were not required. But both of them talk about serving

¹⁵ M/S Motilal Padampat Sugar Mills vs State Of Uttar Pradesh And Ors, 1979 SCR (2) 641.

¹⁶ NHS Foundation Trust v Haywood, [2018] UKSC 22.

¹⁷ P. Dasa Muni Reddy vs P. Appa Rao, 1975 2 SCR 32.

¹⁸ Rev. Msgr, Philip Njaralakkatt Manager vs State of Kerala, (2017) 1 ILR Kerala 547: (2017) 2 KLT 499.

the notice. Rule 17 talks about keeping the notice at a conspicuous place where it could be seen by the recipient and Rule 20 talks about publishing the notice of the summon in a vernacular newspaper, both the rules are made so that the notice is deemed to be served. Hence, sending and serving a notice are two different concepts that need to be looked at carefully. **NHS Foundation Trust v Haywood**¹⁹ was a case where, a lady was entitled to a higher pension if, she could show that she had not been served the notice before her 50th birthday. Since the contract that she had entered with the company had no provisions regarding “when will a notice be deemed to have been served”. The Supreme Court held²⁰ that the lady was entitled to a higher salary and added that it didn't find any merit in the argument that by giving the amount to the lady there would be practical problems. Regardless, the employer was always free to include specific language in the contract regarding the means of notice-giving and the period at which such notices are considered to have been received.

Section 3 of the Indian Contract Act says that an offer can be communicated by any means to the offeree. The fact that such communication should signify to the offeree and the offeror's willingness to do or abstain from doing a particular task will suffice. It can be oral, face-to-face, over call, by a letter even by conduct, or by any specific mode otherwise mentioned. Section 4 of the Indian Contract Act defines completion of communication, the communication of a proposal is complete when it comes to the knowledge of the offeree. It then further defines acceptance and revocation on the part of both the offeror and offeree.

Better communication is beneficial on the part of both parties. It is essential for the parties to know the intentions of each other. This being said, what it means is that parties should be at consensus-ad-idem. Though, this means “meeting of mind” here what this term shows is that a party who is giving an offer, should explicitly lay out the purpose that the contract is serving and should also convey what the parties are expected to do. For further substantiating the argument, in the case of **Lalman Shukla vs Gauri Datt**²¹, it was pronounced by the Allahabad High Court that for a valid acceptance, the person should have worked in lieu of such contract and it can be rightly said that the offeree did not have the knowledge of the offer and no acceptance can occur before the knowledge of the offer.

¹⁹Redmans Solicitors, <https://redmans.co.uk/insights/supreme-court-clarifies-when-notice-of-termination-is-effective-newcastle-upon-tyne-hospitals-nhs-foundation-trust-v-haywood-2018-uksc-22/>, (last visited June 11, 2024).

²⁰ Abhisheak Bansal, Waiver under Contract Act- When Effective-Doctrine of Promissory Estoppel, Acumen Juris, (last visited June 11, 2024).

²¹ Lalman Shukla vs Gauri Datt, (1913) XL ALJR 489 (All.).

VI. INDEMNITY CLAUSE IN A CONTRACT

A contract of Indemnity is one in which an Indemnifier promises to save the Indemnity Holder from losses caused to him either due to the conduct of the Indemnifier himself or by any other person. The above-said definition has been taken verbatim from section 124 of the Indian Contract Act. There are 2 parties in an Indemnity contract, one being the Indemnity holder, the one who is indemnified against any losses and the other is the Indemnifier, the one who promises to indemnify. Indemnity contracts are a species of contingent contract because it is dependent on the happening or not happening of another event for which the Indemnifier has a primary liability as soon as the event happens. An indemnity bond safeguards a party against all the losses a party suffers, provided it is either mentioned in the contract or is tacit by the nature of such contracts, if there is no written contract signed.

Indemnity bonds are absolute in their nature and there is no condition that is prefixed for the execution of an Indemnity bond. Once a liability has accrued on the part of the indemnity holder, the Indemnifier is bound to make the losses that have been made. Through the case of **Gajanan Moreshwar v. Moreshwar Madan**²², it has been clear that there exists an absolute liability on the Indemnifier to indemnify. An excuse that the suit is premature and there is no cause of action before the breach happens is incorrect. Till a court pronounces a judgement, then only the Indemnifier is bound to pay is something that is barred in law. The whole purpose of such a contract is that whenever there is a liability on the indemnity holder, the person should be discharged of it as and then. It is because of such absolute restrictions only, that the clauses regarding such instruments (Indemnity bonds) help in the mitigation of risks and find their place in contracts.

VII. DISPUTE RESOLUTION CLAUSES

As per section 9 of the Civil Procedure Code, all courts are competent to try a case until and unless there is an express or implied bar on the jurisdiction of the court. Also, there exists a natural Jurisdiction of courts under section 20 of the Civil Procedure Code on three grounds. These are:

- Where Cause of action arises.

²² Gajanan Moreshwar Parelkar v. Moreshwar Madan Mantri, (1942) 44 Bom LR 703.

- Place of making and performing the contract.
- Place of business and residence of Defendant.

Parties may choose an appropriate forum according to their convenience to settle disputes. A pre-decided forum along with a place to settle disputes is beneficial for both the parties in a contract. For example, section 28 explicitly excludes an arbitrational award as a restraint to legal proceedings. An arbitrational award can save unnecessary litigation expenses and the time that parties would have wasted if there was no such clause. With a reading of section 23 and section 28 of the Indian Contract Act, it can also be comprehended that an “exclusive jurisdiction” clause can be inserted in an agreement; in the case of **Hakam Singh v. Gammon (India) Ltd**²³ partial restraint in a contract is allowed and as long as the Jurisdiction conferred is one that is within the contours of Section 20 of the CPC, it is very much valid. The same has also been stated in the case of **Raigarh jute**²⁴. In the judgment of **Swastik Gas**²⁵ the much-needed clarity was given by the Supreme Court²⁶ when the court said that it is a settled law, that the stance of the courts regarding words such as ‘alone’, ‘only’, and ‘exclusive’ is immaterial. The court has emphasized on the proposition “that the very existence of a jurisdiction clause in an agreement makes the intention of the parties to an agreement quite clear”. The principle of *expressio unius est exclusion alterius* (expression of one is an exclusion of the other) would be applicable to such cases.

VIII. CONCLUSION

All the above-mentioned clauses can be used are Standard Risk Mitigation clauses. Some minute changes in the drafting can lead to safeguarding from Legal problems. On the other side, an inability to redress a wrongly drafted contract can lead to difficulties. The parties should follow some basic principles that can be useful for curbing any unwanted situations. For example, a contract using highly vocabulist language can be difficult to interpret; The aim should be to use words that can address the issues in a contract and can be understood by both parties with ease. Similarly, a contract having a dispute resolution clause should be comprehended in a way in which both parties have consensus-ad-idem. In such cases, usually,

²³ *Hakam Singh v. Gammon (India) Ltd*, 1971 SCR (3) 314.

²⁴ *Raigarh jute and Textile Mills Ltd v New Haryana Transport*, 1994(0) MPLJ626.

²⁵ *(M/S Swastik Gases Pvt. Ltd v. Indian Oil Corp.Ltd)*, (2013) 9 SCC 32.

²⁶ Akash Nair, *Exclusive Jurisdiction Clause in Contracts*, Mondaq, (last visited June 11, 2024).

the place where the seat of arbitration is agreed becomes the governing law.²⁷ If a company is getting bound by a contract, not only the Legal team but also the other interested stakeholders who are getting affected by the incorporation of the New Contract should be consulted before the signing of the contract. Other Principles may also include addressing the Governing laws of a particular state, whenever there is a contract between different foreign entities, this will make sure that the parties abide by the jurisdiction that has been accepted by the parties, at the earlier stage. Only, Standard Risk Mitigation clauses by themselves cannot ensure insurance to a party from the shortcomings of an improperly drafted contract. Yet, they will surely help in the standardization of the contract and will help in safeguarding the concerned party, in all types of contracts.

²⁷Mark Lakin, Stephenson Harwood, Dispute resolution clauses: drafting principles and concepts, (last visited June 11, 2024).